

The integrative model of Personality and a role of Personality in a Planetary Health context

Liudmila Liutsko¹⁻³, PhD

- 1) ISGlobal, Barcelona, Spain
- 2) UPF, Barcelona, Spain
- 3) CIBERESP, Barcelona, Spain
- 4) MSU, Moscow, Russia

Correspondence to: Liudmila.Liutsko@ISGlobal.org

Abstract /Summary

The aim of this study is twofold: 1) to review and reflect upon emerging trends within integrative personality model, and 2) to propose a broad personality model, that recognises the importance and interdependency of personality and Planetary Health (PH).

The results of a mini-review on “Personality” AND “integral model” covered by the last five years (2012-2017) highlighted important recent trends in personality research. The most popular topics (ranked by frequency of peer-reviewed publications) were related to interactions with the environment (social, cultural, organizational, relational, natural, etc.) and life-style (also QoL); bio-psy-social model and emotions and emotional intelligence.

Based on the observations of a potential bidirectional influence of environment and personality development, an Environmentally Integrative Personality model is extended further with links to the PH concept. Understanding the mechanisms which underlie a personality formation, as well as the bidirectional interactions between environment and person lead to a deeper understanding of the role of ethical dimensions of personal behaviour in a PH perspective. So, it is important to make an insight, from the holistic point of view, into the integrative model of personality considering its bidirectional relationship with broader environment (social + natural).

Key words: personality integrative model; ethical personal behavior; social and natural environment; Planetary Health

1. Introduction: Overview of different approaches and dimensions in personality models

1.1 Definitions of personality and integrative personality models

По одежке встречают, по уму провожают

[Fine dress helps to impress, conversation makes one what he is]

(“Don’t judge the book by its cover”)

The proverb

Given the many branches or subdivisions of science, as well as the difference between a scientific representation and an artistic or casual description, it would be logical to assume that different approaches the representation of Personality as a concept exist. In its most generalized definitions, “personality” is described as:

Personality is the organized, developing system within the individual that represents the collective action of that individual’s major psychological subsystems

(Mayer, 2007, p. 14).

Personality refers to those characteristics of the person that account for consistent patterns of feelings, thinking, and behaving

(Pervin, Cervone & John, 2005, p.6, cited in Mayer, 2007).

In these definitions, “Personality” can be represented by a more complex and a more abstract element. It can be perceived through a global, holistic, approach (when the whole is not just the sum of all components), or a structural-analytical approach.

In different cultures, depending on language, other perceptual differences in meanings of “Personality”, either lexical or etymological, may exist. For example, “Personality” from the etymological point of view of the English language means something “personal” that belongs or refers to a “person”, whereas in Russian, the equivalent for “personality” (“личность”) refers to a “face” (“лик”, “лицо”) though the second meaning in the semantic field of the word (“лицо”) is more general, signifying a “person” as well. In general, the concept of “Personality”, reflects specific behavioral features of a person (a dynamic system of individual behavioral characteristics that contribute to the system), from their more visible forms to the other deeper, or more hidden elements of Personality, of a conscious or unconscious nature. Sometimes (especially in a popular literature) the expression “she/he is a personality” means a charismatic individual who “stands out” in

a crowd owing to their peculiar behavior, values or the efforts they make to attain some high goals. In the psychology of the Soviet period, the concept of Personality was also closely related to some conscious work to be done or efforts to be made for changing for better. Such qualitative change in Personality development was crucial, though this was sometimes driven by environmental stress factors (e.g., temporal unbalances and going out of one's "zone of comfort") (Ivannikov, 2017).

However, in a common-sense context, the meaning of Personality possibly implies what one distinguishes a person alive from a dead body: when we look at a dead body and try to go back in our memories to the image of the person we used to know well, we evoke in our memory his/her smile, voice, gestures, words, etc.... Maybe, for these reasons the Buddhist concept of "personality" is more related to a soul which is not necessarily totally separated from a body (an "alive" one), something that is also seen in yoga practices and other oriental beliefs. The body-mind connection is attracting more attention in the western cultures nowadays. This model is also seen in therapeutic practices and other applications, such as breathing control for relaxation and to prevent anxiety or panic attacks.

The dualistic model of body and mind has been criticized in studies in the area of human behavior by such researchers as Damasio (1994) and Carrió (2002) among others, as per . For example, the study of post-traumatic personality changes (Koponen, Taiminen, Portin, Himanen, Isoniemi, Heinonen, ... & Tenovuo, 2002), ; studies of the influence of genes or neuro-transmitters on emotion, cognition and as a result changes in behavior (Bond, 2001).

Apart from genetic heredity, other important aspects define and strongly affect personality development, such as the immediate social environment (family, friends, school, work, etc...) and more general ones like the socio-cultural component of the determined historical moment the person belongs to. As Trofimova and colleagues (2018) point out, socio-cultural individual differences are influenced by various pro-social biases that also include evaluation or moral judgments.

Generally, a self or a personality can be presented as a multilayer model, similar to a Galaxy (macro) or an atom (micro-level), or analogous to the Eastern European "matryoshka" souvenir (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Multilayer structure of a personality, a Galaxy and an atom: the complex structure of the “self” construction (adapted from Liutsko, 2013¹).

The multilayer approach can be applied to represent both simple as well as complex structures, such as from genes and molecular (micro) perspective, through to representations of a person’s “extensions” in the existing worlds as impressions of his/her thoughts, words and actions, as well as interactions with the social and natural environment.

1.2 Lluís Fonts’ proposal on integrative model of personality (“The red of systems”)

One of the most complete proposals for an integrative model for the different theories and paradigms of Personality in psychological science was proposed by a Catalanian scientist Lluís Font (2002). The article and the book were published in Spanish, and set out the Web of Systems Theory (“la Teoria de la Red de Sistemas” in Spanish) based on two psychobiological systems (horizontal systems and vertical systems). The first group of systems represents the Big Five biological supports or Five Factors Model (FFM). Three of the systems belong to Temperament - inhibitory system, system of rapid activation and activation system that gives support to Anxiety, Hostility and

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Extraversion; the fourth is Self-control - the self-regulatory system that supports Consciousness, and the fifth is the integrative cognitive system, Intelligence (or Openness in FFM). The second group of systems (vertical) consists of 13 subsystems that can be neurophysiological, somatic, emotional, connative or cognitive. The aim of the second group is to provide efficient functioning of the first one, Font's proposed Web of Systems Theory builds on the most influential personality models (in the author's opinion), including: 1) the characteristic model of Neuman and Wiersma (1909); 2) the libidinal typology of Freud (1931); 3) the constitutional model of Kretschmar (1921); 4) the Sheldon model of components (1942); 5) three forms of relationship by Horney (1945): avoidance, struggle and approach; 6) Pavlov's neurophysiological typology (1927); 7) and its reformulation by Strelau (1983); 8) the Eysenck PEN model (1970); 9) the three factors of the second order in the revision by Royce (1973); 10) the NEO model of Costa and McCrae (1985); 11) the three neurological systems described by Gray (1987), 12) the three factors of the empirical analysis of Zuckerman, Kuhlman, Joireman, Teta y Kraft (1993) (as cited in Lluís Fonts, 2001). The Web of Systems Theory by Lluís Fonts is schematically shown in Table 1.

PLEASE INSERT TABLE 1 ABOVE HERE

1.3 Fashion for verbal tests on Personality assessment: What we miss then?

Trofimova and colleagues (2018) claim that verbal tests, as used in FFM, for example, do not use biological perspectives for temperamental dimensions (Neuroticism & Extraversion). However, the dispositional behavior, which is based on a soma readiness to realise the action, can differ from the intentional one: we may wish to do something, but not to have energy or capacity to perform it (Tous & Liutsko, 2014). Dispositional (unconscious) behavior can be measured by physiological methods, including fine motor behavior, which is rarely used compared to other cognitive methods that are applied mainly for conscious dimension of personality. Fine motor behavior, as a motor behavior in psychology is still underdeveloped Rosebaum (2005).

Almost a century ago Mira y Lopez (1923) and Luria (1932) explored somatic correlations with cognition and emotion, that are not widely known for linguistic (the major part of works was published in Portuguese and Spanish) or other socio-historical reasons. Further development of Mira y Lopez's observational and experimental work

was carried out under his Miokinetic Psychodiagnosis (M.K.P., Mira, 1958; Miroshnikov, 1963; Muiños, 2008, as well the digital version of some parts of it as DP-TC test Proprioceptive Diagnostic of Temperament and Character– see description in English in Tous & Liutsko, 2014). This is an alternative or complementary test linked to fine motor movements and precision that is less likely to be faked due to morality judgement or social desirability. For these reasons, the M.K.P. was used in Latina America as part of medical assessment of drivers and other jobs related with responsibility for the safety of others' lives, such as pilots or applicants for a gun license, among others (Tous, Muños, & Liutsko, 2014). Due to graphical performance and output, these methods are also easy to apply to small children or people from different countries, since there is no need to have a good linguistical basis to be able to perform it (Liutsko, Malova, Maldonado, & Tous Ral, 2018). If verbal tests reflect more of what person (or others) think about him or her, miokinetic (or proprioceptive) tests show more dispositional trends of human behavior (even they could be unconscious) (Tous et al., 2014).

1.4. Bio-psy-social models of personality: importance of historico-social and cultural dimensions

Mira y Lopez was a medical worker and psychologist (later one of the first psychiatrists in Spain) who paid attention to education and also supported a psi-bio-social model of personality. For example, he claimed that medical workers would tend to support/fight for (?)for human rights since hunger still was the cause of many deaths in poor countries. Moreover, he emphasized the importance of society and education on general (and particularly on mental) health, saying “it is impossible to have healthy people in ill society” (Liutsko, 2014). Mira stressed to the more social aspects of public health, such as equity, human rights, etc... (Liutsko, 2014); also it was shown that the role a leadership type can play important role for health (Czabanowska, Rethmeier, Lueddeke, Smith, Malho, Otok, & Stankunas, 2014).

Nevertheless, in spite of a bad social environment and trauma, there exists a capacity to restore or renew one's-self via process of resilience (Cyrulnik, 2005) or transformational creativity that helps to find new solutions and survive (Csikszentmihalyi, 1997; Dreifuss-Kattan, 2016). However, adaptation to new changes requires a lot of resources and not all people are able to adapt. This can result in negative consequences, for example, the suicides that took place after moving or

detaching old people from their native places after the Fukushima accident in Japan (Ohto, Maeda, Yabe, Yasumura, & Bromet, 2015). To conclude, Mira was a pioneer in recognizing that both types of environment, social and natural, are linked to human health (including well-being) and can affect it either in a negative or positive way.

1.5 Emerging research on links between the natural environment and human health/well-being, ageing and related cognitive and emotional states, physical activity and sociability

The impact of the Environment on human health has increasingly drawn the attention of Environmental Medicine and Ecological Psychology researchers. These include the natural as well as built-up, artificial or human-created Environments, and also cover their effects on personality (mental health and well-being). For example, exposure to lead and methyl mercury, thalidomide in early pregnancy, misoprostol, valproic acid, maternal rubella infection; the organophosphate insecticide, chlorpyrifos can all result in some psychopathologies (Landrigan, 2010). Likewise, lead and PCBs have been identified as potential risk factors for ADHD (Eubig, Aguiar, & Schantz, 2010); proximity to mercury sources can increase the prevalence in autism (Palmer, Blanchard, & Wood, 2009). Some toxins (e.g., lead, solvents) can cause behavioral disturbances (self-regulation, aggression), and insufficient daylight is associated with increased depressive symptoms (Evans, 2003).

Among the possible positive environment impacts on human health and well-being, green and blue spaces have been shown effect a number of health factors, including: positive emotion and reduction of stress (Gascon, Triguero-Mas, Martínez, Dadvand, Forns, Plasència, & Nieuwenhuijsen, 2015; Lee & Maheswaran, 2011; Van den Berg, Maas, Verheij, & Groenewegen, 2010); ageing (Takano, Nakamura, & Watanabe, 2002); cognition (attention) related to ageing (Dadvand, Tischer, Estarlich, Llop, Dalmau-Bueno, López-Vicente, ... & Rodríguez-Dehli, 2017) and promoting physical activity which is related to health and QoL (Calogiuri & Chroni, 2014; Gill, Hammond, Reifsteck, Jehu, Williams, Adams, ... & Shang, 2013).

Thus, peoples' health and well-being is related also to their natural environment and human action towards the environment, either on individual or collective level finally, as a boomerang can return to themselves or their future generations. This implies a tight link of human ethical behavior implies not only people (or social environment), but should be extended to a Planet itself, promoting a Planetary Health. The concept of

Planetary Health has been formulated recently (publication of Rockefeller Foundation–Lancet Commission on Planetary Health) as “the health of human civilization and the natural systems on which they depend”. Thus, “[a]lterations of climate, water, land and ecosystems are challenging all life on our planet, with serious “implications for human health. The way we think about the planet needs to be revised, as does the approach we take in interacting with it.” (cited in welcoming part of the first issue of the Lancet Journal of Planetary Health, *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 2017).

Based on the above, the present article focuses on the importance of Personality as an integrative model and its role in a Planetary Health context. It pursues two main goals: the first is to review the current “views” on personality integrative models and its components, as described in scientific peer-reviewed publications over the last five years (to screen the modern trends); the second is to integrate of the Personality model within the framework of the Planetary Health to emphasize the ethical human behavior toward other people and natural environment (by adding the results from papers linking health that includes mental health and well-being to natural or artificial environment).

2. Methods

The literature review on an “integrative model of personality” via PubMed search (November 2017) aimed to shed light on the construction of the integrative model of personality and the most “popular” topics within the field. It focused on peer-review publications related to “Personality” AND “integrative model” issues during the past (covering 2012-2017).

First, the main topics of studies were picked up from a number of selected papers and then they were classified into groups as per concepts described in papers. Secondly, the selected papers were read through again and afterwards the topics covered in each article were re-counted according to the previous list of covered topics by each article (for example, topics defined for one selected in the analysis paper were the following ones: “personality traits (FFM, big five, NEO, etc.)”, “social environment” and “mental health”). “Integrative Personality” was mainly explained by two topics (since there should be at least two parameters related to personality to integrate); but sometimes by more dimensions (three, four or five), and in exceptional cases four topics related to personality dimensions and their extrinsic and intrinsic factors of influence and were integrated in a study by researchers.

Finally, based on the obtained results and a general reflection on the factors, as well, extending and complementing the search towards effects of natural/artificial environment on human health (mental health and well-being which is also linked to behavioural individual and personality patterns); a contextual model of the important role of Personality (including its ethical behavioural component) in a Planetary Health context is suggested.

2.1. The overall picture from the bibliographical review

A complete review of all existing models of personality as well as of all attempts to construct its integrative model is beyond the scope of this paper. This article, nevertheless, can make a contribution to the creation of such a review. The bibliographical review was carried out to gain insight into the latest trends for the integrative approaches to the concept of “Personality”, to obtain some “screening” of modern tendencies and views within this topic and views. The information search was performed in a medical context (PubMed) since the global topic of this article is related to the interactions between personality and Planetary Health.

The search was done via PubMed sources with advanced search using the key words “personality” AND “integrative model” (November 2017): 520 entries were found dated between 2012 and 2017 back to 2012; 205 titles from these were pre-selected on the basis of not being directly relevant to the subject of personality integrated models. Further analysis of the abstract content of the pre-selected papers by titles led to the selection of 100 abstracts, from which 72 full papers on integrative model of personality were finally chosen. Two abstracts had to be excluded as they did not bring over any new points (they were mere opinions in some replies to the previous publications, Letters to Editors). As a result, 70 abstracts and full papers were included into the bibliographical review to examine the “popularity” (by frequency) of topics developed under the key words “Personality” AND “integrative model” (Figure 1).

<PLEASE, INSERT ABOUTHERE FIGURE 1>

Figure 2. Flow of selection analysis for a mini-review on “Personality” AND “integrative model”.

3. Results

3.1. The overall picture from the bibliographical mini-review

The initial list of identified topics of the selected papers related to Personality integrative model concept accounted for 21, but following an analytical review “scan”, some of the topics were merged because they had similar context, leading to a final list of 18 topics (Table 2, 2a). The second analysis counted the frequency of each previously identified topic for each of the selected papers. The list of topics was then ranked in accordance with the frequency of their explicit appearance in the reviewed studies, as represented in Table 2 (with bibliographical references, Table 2a in Annex).

The resultant “Personality” model, was a result of integrating a combination of any of topics that reflect specific dimension/s of personality or self and/or to other intrinsic or external/ environmental parameters that could influence on its development either alterations. The majority of papers covered two or three topics, but sometimes, in exceptional cases, four or even five topics were discussed by the same paper.

PLEASE, INSERT Table 2 HEREBABOUT

The first three most popular topics integrated into Personality were closely related to the Environment (mainly social, cultural, organizational and included family/friends/teachers/other types of relationship) and life style (including quality of life; QoL) followed by Bio-Psycho-social models as well as Emotional and self-regulation patterns (emotional intelligence (EI), self-control, tolerance, resilience, (mal) adaptive behavior, personality types -A, etc.) (Table 2).

Another major block of interactions and developmental dependence was related to social environment, and less (but not least by means) the role of natural environment on personality development and formation. While we see, that moral behavior was not a key research issue, it has been identified as a crucial issue in a personality behaviour change that should be included in a socio-cultural dimension of personality Tromifova *et al.* (2018) and plays an important role in formation of personality type that will respect their social and natural environment (Liutsko, 2013) and, thus, reflected in human actions, will help to conserve a Planetary Health (Figure 3).

3.2. Proposal for the model describing the role of Personality for a Planetary Health

A person is an element of a bigger constructs, such as society or humankind, the evolution and development of which depends on the state of the planet Earth and the living conditions on it, including social environment. Owing to both, an exponential growth of human inhabitants on the Earth and their activity on the planet, makes environmental issues a key challenge for preserving the planet and all living organisms on it. This growth in human activity comes at a price in terms of our health, because our health also depends on our environment (Calogiuri & Chroni, 2014; Evans, 2003; Eubig *et al.*, 2010; Gascon *et al.*, 2015; Palmer *et al.*, 2009; Van den Berg *et al.*, 2010). If it was possible to change individual behavior towards to higher awareness of maintaining the sustainability of Environment, our own health as well as Planetary Health would change, which would change another link of this chain - society and another link of the chain - Environment.

Figure 3 represents a symbolic model that integrates a personality (P, in a core of the model) and personality growth; individual values and behavior; and personality interrelationships with social environment (SE), natural environment (NE) and artificial natural environment (ANE) that appeared thanks to human activity (new constructions and alteration of natural environment landscapes). Because people live within social, NE and ANE, their actions turn back, like a boomerang, causing positive or negative effects on people’s health (Figure 3).

<PLEASE, INSERT ABOUTHERE FIGURE 3>

Figure 3. P (personality) interdependence with SE (social environment) and G (genetics), NE (natural environment), with ANE (artificial natural environment or secondary nature, created by humans)

Legend: P – Personality, SE – social environment, G – genetics, NE – natural environment, ANE – artificial natural environment; “->” stands for a relation (also shown by arrows on the diagram).

As for the model proposed above, we need to define a kind of “Environmental-sustainability-aware” behavior or a quality of personality with respect to the concept of Planetary Health.. The present paper shows that links between environment (social and natural) and personalities are important also in terms to emphasise the importance of considering ethical dimension of personal behavior or personality “environmental-friendly and sustainable” concept with regards of promoting a Planetary Health.

General discussion, reflections and conclusions

The first part of the article refers to attempts and possibilities to connect different aspects of personality, the topic which many minds of professionals’ marvel about; and attempts to bridge gaps and consider both inter-personal variability and intra-personal variability in behavior (Baumert et al., 2017). Some aspects of personality behavior are less developed, such as automatic (reflexive) vs. controlled (reflective) processes of human behavior, difference of which was mentioned by Corr (2010); motor control in psychology which still requires more attention (Rosenbaum, 2005) and moral or ethical aspects of human behavior with respect to socio-cultural (Trofimova, 2018) and natural environment as considered in this paper.

Researchers are attempting to create integrative models of personality (Baumert et al., 2017; Font, 2002 to mention some) where the basis of genetic-neurological behavior is linked to somatic, emotional and cognitive processes. However, in the science of human behavior, developmental processes and their implications in and links to historical-and-socio-cultural processes as defined by Vygotsky should also be developed (Perinat, 2011), which, in the light of a multilayer personality model, affect the personality formation (Liutsko, 2013; Trofimova, 2018).

The major part of Personality topic research was and still is dedicated to either a personal change and development (one’s personality, creativity, intelligence, motivational and transformational aspects) or interpersonal relationships (organizational, social, politic, cultural, etc.) with a description of or a focus on negative aspects of a person’s health (mental health) or on other facets (criminology and clinical psychology). Ecological psychology together with education could build bridges

between personality and social and natural environments, making thus a personality model broader and linking it to a planetary ecosystem.

To sum up, Personality integrative models could be created on all range of scales - from micro to macro making attempts:

- 1) to link all dimensions and variety of human complex nature (from genetics to social level), and
- 2) to develop a model of behavior of a “nature-sustainability-aware” and moral or ethical personality, which would reflect constructive life-style and accomplishment of one’s *self* in a beneficial way, or at least not harmful or destructive way to our planet and all living organisms on it, as well as to a Planetary Health.

In this concept, “nature-sustainability-awareness” would mean a kind of a balance between human own benefits and human egotistic behavior on the one hand, and consideration of other forms of life and the life of diverse planetary organisms on the other hand.

Acknowledgments

I’m very thankful to Prof. Ph. Corr for his initiative to propose such a topic of a high challenge in Personality research. In addition, I’d like to express my sincere gratitude to Nina Rashidova for some linguistic corrections she kindly offered to make in the initial version of this manuscript. Many thanks to five anonymous reviewers, whose comments helped to improve the manuscript. My deepest appreciation to Prof. Deborah Oughton for her final corrections and suggestions to improve the article.

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ANNEX

Table 2a. Bibliographical references in mini-review per each category listed.

Ranking position	Topics	Bibilographical References	Nº of sources
1	Environment and life style (mainly social, cultural, organizational, including QoL, relationships)	1, 2, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 13, 15, 16, 17, 20, 21, 22, 24, 25, 31, 32, 34, 35, 36, 43, 45, 46, 48, 50, 51, 55, 59, 62, 67, 69, 70	34
2	Bio-psy-social model; Psychopathology (PTSD, Anxiety, Depression, TOC, bipolar, stress, insomnia, ADHD, addiction, bulimia, anorexia, psychosis)	1, 2, 3, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 18, 19, 26, 28, 32, 35, 37, 38, 42, 43, 45, 47, 48, 50, 51, 52, 53, 58, 59, 65, 68	32
3	Emotional and self-regulation (EI, self-control, self-esteem, self-cognition, tolerance, resilience, (mal)adaptive behaviour, personality types -A, etc.)	5, 7, 8, 9, 13, 16, 17, 21, 23, 28, 32, 33, 34, 36, 38, 41, 42, 51, 52, 61, 63, 65, 69	23
4	Big Five (+ its comparison with other models)	5, 12, 13, 15, 27, 30, 31, 38, 44, 45, 55, 56, 63, 64, 66	15
5	Neuroscience, Neurobiology, Neuropsychology (cognitive and affective), neural correlates (Gray's model, etc.)	4, 10, 30, 42, 49, 51, 53, 61, 65	10
6	Dynamic models of personality, Plasticity	26, 38, 40, 42, 44, 51, 62	7
7	DSM, ICD	11, 26, 27, 66, 68	5
8	Neuroendocrinology, genetics and molecular	1, 2, 37, 56	4
8	Believes, values	4, 6, 45, 55	4
8	Temperament and character, psycho-biological model (Cloninger's model, TCI, ...)	37, 39, 62, 64	4
8	"Narratives", reflective description (self-perception, self-criticism, self-stereotyping, self-compassion)	25, 45, 60, 67	4
8	Somatization, internalization	7, 14, 18, 20	4
8	Perception (spatial, visual, emotional, kineastetic, proprioceptive, pain)	45, 54, 65, 69	4
9	IQ, Creativity	20, 29, 56	3

10	IRT (Item response theory)	11, 64	2
11	Phenotypes, other physiology	40	2
11	Conscious vs. unconscious / automatic vs. controlled Collective vs. Individualistic	57	1
11	Collective vs. Individualistic	61	1

Table 1 Structural matrix of systems and factors (Ll. Font, translation and adaptation to English by Liutsko, L.)

DIMENSIONS		x CORRELATES Vertical systems													
		Neurophysiological	Somatical			Emotional			Connative			Cognitive			
		Biochemical Electrical Neurophysiological system	Morphological	Physiological	Psychomotor	Instinctive	Affective	Interpersonal (social)	Volitional (energetic system)	Behavioural (reactive system)	Ethical	Self-perceptive	Processual (strategic system)	Cognitive	
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	
Horizontal systems	TEMPERAMENT	ANXIETY Inhibitory system BIS (Melancholic)	Serotonin Noradrenalin	Ectomorphy Leptosomatic	Blush Pale Sweat	Tension Tremor Excitability Retractable mobility	Avoidance Conservation	Negative emotionality Fear	Shyness Embarrassment	Asthenia Fatigability	Behavioral inhibition	Superego Obsessive	Self under esteem	Cognitive inhibition Worry Focal attention	Logico-mathematical Intelligence Gf
		A	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9	A10	A11	A12	A13
H		HOSTILITY System of rapid activation, FFS (Choleric)	MAO Testosterone Enhancers	Mesomorphy Athletic	Shocks (Fear-potentiated startle) Spasms Arrhythmia	Paralysation	Aggression Defense Territoriality	Hardness Aversion	Dominance Authoritarianism	Competitiveness Ambition	Impulsivity Impatience	Self (ego) Narcissistic Type Rebellion Antisocial	Hypertrophy of Self Challenge Suspicion	Intuition Automation Visual style Synthesis Cognitive speed	Creative visual-spatial intelligence musical right hemisphere
H1		H2	H3	H4	H5	H6	H7	H8	H9	H10	H11	H12	H13		

		CHARACTER (Self)												
	EXTRAVERSION Activatory system BAS (Sanguine)	Dopamine MAO	Endomorphy Pyknic type	Associated with sexual Jealousy, hunger, thirst, etc.	Expansive mobility	Approximation Sensations Seeking (Nutrition, Positive emotion Tenderness	Sociability	Activity Energy	Surge Spontaneity	"id" Erotic type Bohemia	self overvaluation	Openness Diffuse attention Holistic style	Linguistic intelligence Memory and learning Gc	
	E	E1	E2	E3	E4	E5	E6	E7	E8	E9	E10	E11	E12	E13
	SELF-DISCIPLINE Self-regulatory system (Phlegmatic)	Neurophysiological control	Morphological control	Physiological control	Psychomotor control	Impulses control	Emotional control	Social control	Voluntary control Self-dominion	Control of behaviour Responsibility	Moral control Scrupulousness	Self-image control	Control of cognitive strategies	Cognitive controls
	C	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13
	INTELLECT Integrative Cognitive system (Intelligence)	Intelligence A Neuro-physiological Intelligence	Body perceptual intelligence	Functional Body Intelligence	Psychomotor intelligence Kinesthetic body intelligence	Instinctive intelligence	Affective intelligence Intrapersonal intelligence	Social intelligence Interpersonal intelligence	Executive intelligence	Adaptive intelligence	Moral intelligence Moral awareness	Self-perceptive intelligence	Strategic intelligence	General Intelligence C.I.
	I	I1	I2	I3	I4	I5	I6	I7	I8	I9	I10	I11	I12	I13
		Neurophysiological intelligence	Somatic intelligence			Emotional Intelligence			Behavioral intelligence (contextual, judgment)			Cognitive Intelligence		

Table 2. Frequency of topics in peer-reviewed bibliographical search for “personality” and “integrative models”

Ranking position	Topics	Nº of studies	%	Main explanatory mechanisms of affects			
				Individual	Social	Biological	Psychological
1	Environment and life style	34	49%	x	x		x
2	Bio-psy-social model; Psychopathology (PTSD, Anxiety, Depression, TOC, bipolar, stress, insomnia, ADHD, addiction, bulimia, anorexia, psychosis)	32	46%	x	x	x	x
3	Emotional and self-regulation (EI, self-control, self-esteem, self-cognition, tolerance, resilience, (mal)adaptive behaviour, personality types -A, etc.)	23	33%	x			x
4	Big Five (+ its comparison with other models)	15	21%	x			x
5	Neuroscience, Neurobiology, Neuropsychology (cognitive and affective), neural correlates (Gray's model, etc.)	10	14%	x		x	
6	Dynamic models of personality, Plasticity	7	10%	x			x
7	DSM, ICD	5	7%	x		x	x
8	Neuroendocrinology, genetics and molecular	4	6%	x		x	x
8	Believes, values	4	6%	x		x	x
8	Temperament and character, psycho-biological model (Cloninger's model, TCI, ...)	4	6%	x			x
8	"Narratives", reflective description (self-perception, self-criticism, self-stereotyping, self-compassion)	4	6%	x			x
8	Somatization, internalization	4	6%	x		x	
8	Perception (spatial, visual, emotional, kineastetic, proprioceptive, pain)	4	6%	x			x
9	IQ, Creativity	3	4%	x	x		x
10	IRT (Item response theory)	2	3%	x			x
10	Phenotypes, other physiology	1	1%	x	x		x
11	Conscious vs. unconscious / automatic vs. controlled	1	1%	x		x	
11	Collective vs. Individualistic	1	1%	x	x		x

Legend: QoL – Quality of Life; PTSD - Posttraumatic stress disorder; OCD - Obsessive-compulsive disorder; ADHD - Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder; DSM - Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders; ICD – International Classification of Diseases; CTI – Character-Temperament Inventory; IQ – Intelligence Coefficient